

Advanced Door Area Monitoring

Udo Birk¹

¹*University of Applied Sciences of the Grisons, Chur, Graubünden, Switzerland*

ABSTRACT

Door Area Monitoring is an important focus of automated door manufacturers. Presently available door area analytics can not only detect a person wishing to pass through the door, but also discriminate the speed and direction of travel. We use a miniaturized door automation system to study such systems far beyond the conventional detection capabilities required for opening and closing the door: Doors are only partially opened where needed, and at a higher level, the results of image and ranging sensor data evaluation such as gender, age, customer identification etc. can be fed into smart building surveillance.

KEYWORDS: 2D and 3D cameras, door area monitoring, door sensors, hardware virtualization, miniaturized demonstrator

INTRODUCTION

Smart sensors on doors and gates in public areas or on company premises monitor our environment ubiquitously and let us effortlessly pass in and out of buildings or monitor the surrounding area, for example to distinguish whether a person wants to pass through the door or walk past it. Novel photonics sensors call for new solutions in automated area surveillance. High-resolution cameras or 3D imaging sensors provide the means to shift from pure object detection to higher-level depth perception, motion direction analysis, user monitoring and user identification. With increased computation power of single board computers, it is now possible to employ modern approaches for evaluation of 3D scenes. The aim of the presentation is to give an insight into current image sensors and image analysis technology for door area surveillance, and to address the challenges and perspectives of current and future applications. For this we use a miniaturized door automation system which is capable to demonstrate such advanced use cases in a close-to-realistic scenario.

CONCEPT

Fig. 1 depicts the general concept of the door area monitoring system (a), and its virtualized implementation (b). A sensor (2D area sensor or 3D ranging sensor) is located on top of an automated door. The sensor potentially has two functions: First, it acts as a surveillance sensor in order to detect a person which aims at passing through the door. Second, it acts as a safety sensor by continuously monitoring the area between the open door wings, in order to avoid accidental closing of the door whilst a person is in the interspace.

Miniaturized automated door: In a conceptual study, we have implemented a miniaturized version of the automated door and the door area monitoring system. As a representation of the door hardware, the wings of the door are projected onto a computer monitor, and the automated door can be animated on the computer screen using a suitable computer program.

Virtualized door wings: The door is virtualized in a python environment as python classes for the two separate wings, each door wing responding to “OPEN” and “CLOSE” commands, as well as to the commands “MOVE TO POSITION X” with specific positions. The door wing closes automatically after a defined period of time, unless further “OPEN” or “MOVE TO” commands are received. The commands can live be given via an attached keyboard. For this, suitable keyboard shortcuts are defined.

Physical door sensor: The door monitoring system is represented by a physical webcam which is positioned on top of the computer monitor; the sensor delivers images of 640 x 480 pixels at a frame rate of 30 Hz. The webcam is connected to a PC, and a python script is evaluating the images received. The position of the object in front of the door is determined from these images, and evaluated with respect to an anticipated aim to pass through the door. If such an aim is detected, it is translated into a command, addressing a single door wing or both door wings as required. The commands are then injected into the door control software. We use the python module “pyautogui” to translated the commands into their corresponding keyboard shortcut commands (see “Virtualized door wings”).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The schematics of our demonstrator setup is depicted in Fig. 1(b). In our setup, the following components are combined: A Logitech C290 Webcam is delivering images from a 2D area sensor. A 24"-Monitor is employed in place of a physical door, and the door wings are embedded in a more-or-less realistic scenario within a shopping mall. Two independent software programs are used to control the virtualized door and to read-out and evaluate the webcam images. Within the image analysis software, different modes are available to address

the concept of smart-sensors operating at different intelligence levels, ranging from simple detection (both door wings open fully), to left/right detection (each door wing opens fully, but independently of each other), to local detection (door wings are opened independently to fixed positions, e.g. half open, fully open), to position detection (door wings open only as far as needed), to advanced detection (objects in front of the door are recognized, direction of travel is detected, door wings follow the direction of travel).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The demonstrator is able to detect dummy objects (e.g. using a miniaturized toy figure) and to determine the position with respect to the virtualized door. We could show that the system can be employed in a real-time scenario, where the virtualized door responds to the results of the image evaluation, and the response time is suitable for a realistic impression of the door actions. In its present configuration, the system features a 30 Hz image frame rate in a non-real-time operating system, resulting potentially in a high latency. The evaluation program however, is running on a laptop PC, which has far more computation power than the embedded solutions of state-of-the-art door automation systems. Our demonstrator features separation of the two systems used to control door operation and image evaluation, which allows us to assess each component independently.

Figure 1: Advance Door Area Monitoring applies 2D or 3D sensor technology and advanced sensor analytics to ensure safety and to extract advanced traffic information such as direction and speed or a person, as well as potentially additional features such as age, gender, and even ID of a person. (a) General layout of the door area monitoring system with the sensor located above the door. (b) Miniaturized door with sensor (webcam) on the top and virtualized door wings displayed on a computer monitor. Door wings are e.g. operated according to people entering the ROIs defined in the acquired webcam images. The ROIs are highlighted in different colors (area1-3).

CONCLUSIONS

We could show that using virtualization of the door hardware together with a physical image sensor, a miniaturized setup of the automation system could be implemented. We could demonstrate that the system can be used to test performance; it is also suitable for demonstration of additional advanced features of the door area monitoring system, such as detection of the direction of travel, recognition of different objects, and more.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded by the University of Applied Sciences of the Grisons.

CONTACT

* Udo Birk; phone: +41 81 286 37 97; udo.birk@fhgr.ch